

Interview - Research Data Alliance (RDA)

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About this work

The BOOST EDS project, [funded by UKRI and supported by DSIT](#), aimed to pilot a range of measures to address issues of data findability, traceability, accessibility and interoperability, to improve data sharing and access across disciplines. Conducted from late 2023 to March 2025, the project consisted of five work packages, with one work package dedicated to user centred approaches in the context of environmental data services. The work was undertaken by members of the NERC Environmental Data Service (EDS).

This is a summary report to provide supporting information to the overarching report - User centred approaches for environmental data services: embedding co-creation and collaboration (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15115280>)

Summary

This document describes an interview undertaken as part of the context setting work. You can find a synthesis of all other interviews here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15102198>

Interview: Research Data Alliance (RDA)

Meeting date: 04/03/2025

We spoke to a research scientist based in Indiana University at the Luddy School of Informatics, Computing, and Engineering who previously led the Engagement Interest Group at RDA. They have a background in social sciences and has transitioned to all things data.

Their research focuses on emerging technologies, digital media, and data practices. They work on interdisciplinary projects that promote open science, data preservation, and data sharing. Additionally, they apply their language and regional expertise to analyze digital narratives.

Approach to co-creation in projects

Supporting interdisciplinary data:

- Involvement in science projects from the start
 - Document pain points, go in all meetings and observe
- Then try to build tools to address these
 - challenges here - research (at US universities) very siloed - used to using proprietary software with access restrictions
 - Very difficult to encourage people to use new tools
 - E.g. social scientist uses SPSS proprietary, restricted access tool whereas data scientist uses R/python, the two groups spend a lot of time exchanging work
- Instead of software tools, they provided recommendations - difficulty with restricted software and implementing new software tools, this gave more practical help

- To encourage expertise sharing and communication using the same language, need someone in the team embedded in the project from the start who has understanding of the full data lifecycle, e.g. data manager with analytical skills who understands the project's data collection methods etc.
- Design thinking
- Workshops to engage users

Challenges

- Engaging users - finding people who are interested, particularly who work entirely in domain science research
- Human component
- Funding - getting support from domain science
- Divide between data managers and curators with scientists
- Dependence on certain softwares, access restricted silos

Resources

The SEAD project (Sustainable Environment - Actionable Data)

- https://www.nsf.gov/awardsearch/showAward?AWD_ID=0940824&HistoricalAwards=false (funder's page)
- <https://sead2.ncsa.illinois.edu/> (legacy project website)

Engaging Researchers with Data Management: The Cookbook
<https://www.openbookpublishers.com/books/10.11647/obp.0185>

RDA activities report –
<https://inkouper.blogspot.com/2014/11/4th-rda-plenary-breakout-session-on.html>

Project to support interdisciplinary data curation and our recommendations
<https://inkouper.github.io/ihcr-data-curation/>